

Determination and characterization of extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Escherichia coli* in fish and pork sold from selected public markets of Cavite: A comparative analysis

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Abstract

Filipinos, being in an agricultural country, are undeniably meat and fish lovers. Pork is the most consumed livestock and poultry product while fish is number one in the marine products in CALABARZON. However, these products may carry a type of bacteria called extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Escherichia coli*, which can cause infections in humans. This study wants to determine if there is extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Escherichia coli* in pork and fish meat samples sold in public markets in Cavite and compare the groups to show how much of this bacteria is present in these samples. Procedures include isolation and culture using Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth for enrichment. Subcultures are done using MacConkey to differentiate the lactose fermenter from non-lactose fermenter. Eosin methylene blue is used for further identifying *E. coli*, and biochemical test was utilized for manual bacterial identification. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was done using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. This helps screen ESBL and see how resistant the bacteria might be to different antibiotics. The double disk synergy test was used to observe the presence of the ESBL phenotypes. The limit of the study is the detection of the extended spectrum beta-lactamase phenotype and will not include their genomic characteristics. This study only focused on ESBL producing *E. coli* in retail meats specifically pork and fish. Other bacterial contaminants that were not covered in this study were not determined.

Keywords: Determination; Characterization; Extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Escherichia coli*; Fish; Pork.

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Introduction

Infection is one of the main human health issues worldwide. Most of these infectious diseases are caused by bacteria. The discovery of antibiotics was an achievement in treating infectious diseases and helped save countless lives (Ojer-Usoz et al., 2017). Antibiotics are widely used for infectious disease therapy, control, and prevention. It is an antibacterial agent that can either inhibit or destroy bacterial growth. However, improper use and overuse of antibiotics can lead to bacterial resistance to antibiotics.

A major concern for public health is the rise of bacterial resistance because it makes chronic diseases difficult to treat and raises the cost of healthcare. When the bacterium becomes resistant, it either protects itself from the action of the medication or it neutralizes the medication. Thus, incidents of multi-drug resistance are also emerging nowadays. Some bacteria are resistant to many different antibiotics that could attack different parts of the bacteria (Shrestha et al., 2017). It is a high-threat for public health. Infections with MDR are hard to treat since few or even no treatment options remain.

Pathogenic multi drug-resistant bacteria are increasing worldwide. One example is extended spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) producing *Enterobacteriaceae*. They do this by making enzymes like beta-lactamase, which break down the four-ring structure of antibiotics losing its ability to kill the bacteria. These enzymes can break down drugs like penicillin, first, second, and third-generation cephalosporins, and monobactams. However, beta-lactamase inhibitors like clavulanic acid can stop this process (Harris et al., 2015). *Escherichia coli* is the most common cause of infections among the *Enterobacteriaceae* family and has become the main type of bacteria that produces ESBL (Ojer-Usoz et al., 2017). There has been an increase in resistant *E. coli* over the past few decades, especially those that produce ESBL.

According to the World Health Organization (2014), ESBL-producing *E. coli* is the most common cause of bloodstream infections and urinary tract infections in both community and hospital settings, leading to higher mortality rates, increased costs, and longer hospital stays (Aliyu et al., 2016). Using too many antibiotics in humans, animals used for food, and the environment cause ESBL which spreads both inside and outside hospitals.

Filipinos, being in an agricultural country, are undeniably meat and fish lovers. Pork is the most consumed livestock and poultry product, while fish topped the marine products in CALABARZON (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2017). Pork and fish represent more of a human protein source. However, these products may serve as a key medium for transfer from food-producing animals to consumers of multi-drug resistant bacteria that can cause infections to humans. Meat can be contaminated during improper handling, dressing and washing, unsanitary condition, and unhygienic meat distribution practices. Resistant bacteria can move to humans through eating undercooked meat or by touching contaminated surfaces. Contamination of retail meats with ESBL-producing *E. coli* has been found in many countries (Morris et al., 2014).

Using antibiotics in fish farming has led to the spread of bacteria that are resistant to many drugs (Heuer et al., 2009 as cited by Elhadi, 2016). When people eat these fish, the bacteria can enter the human gut. Poor hygiene in places where fish are handled, stored, and sold makes this problem worse (Saad et al., 2020). A high amount of resistance genes in food-producing animals is reported because of the overuse of antimicrobial drugs (Aliyu et al., 2016). Therefore, humans can get infected with ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* bacteria from food-producing animals and food of animal-origin (Reuland et al., 2014).

This study aims to observe if extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Escherichia coli* is present in raw fish and pork meat products sold in selected public markets in Cavite. It also wants to find out how much *E. coli* is found in these fish and pork meat products. This study may help this community by raising their awareness on the presence of ESBL producers in meats from public markets of Cavite and its possible health risks upon consumption. This will lead them to have a basis in taking preventive measures to minimize the cause of illness. Furthermore, it may be used as a supplemental literature for future research about ESBL microorganism producers.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the presence and level of ESBL producing *E. coli* in meat samples – pork and fish.

Scope and Delimitations

The study is limited only to raw fish and pork meat samples that are obtained from selected public markets in Cavite namely: Zapote Public Market, Kadiwa Market, Binakayan Market, Imus Public Market, and Naic Public Market. Three (3) pork and three (3) fish samples are obtained from each mentioned public market which sums up to thirty (30) meat samples. The anatomical site of the samples where the specimens were taken only comprised of the tissue sample, specifically the meat. Other parts, such as fish intestines, skin, gills, and liver, were not utilized in this study. Each meat sample is tested only for *Escherichia coli*; other bacterial contaminants are not within the scope. To identify if the isolated *E. coli* is an ESBL producer, the study only involves characterizing the *E. coli* based on its phenotype and not on its genotype. This study is limited only to collecting the samples straight from the vendors; the researchers no longer interviewed the vendors on where the meat products came from, how they were delivered or how they were stored.

Review of Related Literature

ESBL producing E. coli

Escherichia coli is a type of bacteria that is gram-negative, can live without oxygen, and is rod-shaped. It is a type of coliform bacteria that is commonly found in the lower intestines of people and animals, as well as in the environment and food. This bacterium is harmless in most situations and aids in food digestion. However, some harmful types of *E. coli* can cause diarrhea when people eat contaminated food or drink contaminated water. Although many people think of *E. coli* in terms of food poisoning, it can also lead to pneumonia and urinary tract infections with about 75% to 95% affecting them.

E. coli spreads into the environment through feces. These bacteria grow fast in fresh feces when there is oxygen, and they increase a lot in three days. However, after that, their numbers begin to drop slowly. The main way that harmful bacterial strains cause illness is through fecal-oral transmission. Cells can live for a specified amount of time outside the body which makes them potentially bacterial for both food and environmental fecal contamination. *E. coli* is a type of bacteria that has a thin layer of peptidoglycan and an outer membrane in its cell wall, which makes it a gram-negative bacteria. When stained, it takes up the color of the safranin counterstain and turns out to be pink. The outer membrane helps protect the bacteria from some antibiotics, like penicillin. *E. coli* is one of the bacteria that can cause many different infections and foodborne illnesses that have become a big source of bacteria that produce ESBLs. The rise of antibiotic resistance caused by *E. coli* can cause serious implications for public health leading to treatment failures in clinical settings (Elena et al., 2018).

E. coli infections often start from the affected person (auto-infection). Some types of bacteria that are hard to treat with antibiotics or cause more serious illnesses can pass from animals to humans through food or between people. *E. coli* can become resistant in two main ways: either by mutation through fluoroquinolone antibiotics, or by acquisition of genetic elements from other bacteria through broad-spectrum antibiotics like ampicillin or amoxicillin, and also to third-generation cephalosporins. Resistance to these cephalosporins is mostly because of special enzymes called extended spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs), which destroy many beta-lactam antibiotics. These enzymes can move between different bacteria and even between different kinds of bacteria. Carbapenems are usually the only antibiotics that work well against serious infections caused by *E. coli* strains (WHO, 2014).

ESBL-Ec is a new type of bacteria that can spread from animals to humans and is resistant to many antibiotics, making it a big problem in treating infections today. A large number of *E. coli* infections that spread through the bloodstream in humans come from food animals. It also causes urinary tract infections and is associated with higher death rates, more hospital stays, fewer treatment choices, longer infections, and more treatment failures (Aliyu et al., 2016).

E. coli is a major type of bacteria that pollutes water. It comes from human and animal waste getting into water sources. Fish products can become contaminated either from being in polluted water or from using water that is not safe to drink during their preparation or processing. *E. coli* can cause many types of infections in humans, including food poisoning. These illnesses can range from diarrhea to serious conditions like hemorrhagic colitis and hemolytic uremic syndrome, which are linked to a type of *E. coli* called Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (Gupta et al., 2013).

Fish and related products, like pork, can be a health risk because they often carry harmful bacteria on their surface or inside. These infections can happen if they are not handled properly or cooked incorrectly. Around 90% of fish farming happens in countries with poor hygiene and weak rules on how antibiotics are used. This leads to antibiotics ending up in sewages, which can pollute the environment. Fish farms are often near the coast where there is already a lot of water pollution from human and animal waste. These waste materials contain bacteria with antibiotic resistance genes that can spread and contaminate water (Boss et al., 2016).

Agricultural practices are seen as a major reason for the spread of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) around the world. Aquatic animals such as fish play a key role in the spread of AMR. In countries like Uganda, there is a push to increase aquaculture production, leading to more intensive farming systems that might involve using antibiotics preventively. The use of antimicrobial agents in aquaculture for prevention and to help fish grow has been reported. Water bodies are 'meeting points' for humans, land animals, and aquatic animals, and could play an important role in the emergence, spread, and maintenance of AMR. Fish can show how microbes interact in water. Nile tilapia (*O. niloticus*) is the most farmed and eaten fish and is economically essential. However, *E. coli* found in the gut of *tilapia* can contribute to the spread and maintenance of antimicrobial resistance (Kikomeko et al., 2016).

Antimicrobial agents are often given to fish, either mixed with their food or directly. The doses used for fish can be higher than those used for livestock. Not only do these medicines leave behind fish products, but also leftover food and fish waste that still has some of the antimicrobials in which it can stay in the surrounding water and sediment for a long time. About 70-80% of the antibiotics given to fish end up in the water. This can change the types of microbes that are present there (Watts et al., 2017).

Research Gap

There have been a number of significant studies that have recently been done about ESBL from the food of animal-origin. However, what makes this study different from those is that the researchers focused on the determination of ESBL in pork and fish and compared the significant level of ESBL between the two samples. International studies were more focused in poultry and other food origins as a sample (Davis et al., 2018; Martínez-Chávez et al., 2015; Soufi et al., 2011). Only limited studies have been done in retail pork especially in fish. In the Philippines, studies about ESBL were more focused on clinical and hospital settings (Cornista et al., 2019; Cruz et al., 2014; Tiongco et al., 2018). Another gap observed by the researchers is with regards to the location of the studies; thus, the researchers used samples from selected public markets of Cavite where information on ESBL is limited.

Methodology

In this study, the researchers utilized two main methods: sampling and experimentation. The researchers collected 15 samples of fish and 15 samples of pork retail meat products from selected public markets in Cavite. From these samples, the researchers then performed an experiment to identify the presence of extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Escherichia coli*.

The traditional procedures performed are as follows: Culture Media Preparation; Collection and Processing of Samples; Bacterial Isolation, Identification and Characterization; and Determination of Antibiotic Susceptibility Test. Samples of the study were collected from public markets in Cavite specifically in Bacoor Public Market, Imus Public Market, Binakayan Public Market, Kadiwa Market, and Naic Public Market.

Procedures

Sample Collection

A total of 30 samples, including 15 pork and 15 fish, were determined to see if they had ESBL *E. coli*. Only pork meat and three kinds of fish (*Tilapia*, *Galunggong*, and *Hasa-hasa*) were collected. All the samples were bought from different vendors in selected markets in Cavite. They were kept in an ice box to keep them fresh and stop any harmful bacteria from growing.

Isolation and Identification

Fish and pork were cleaned externally with tap water. Muscle from the mid area region of fish was collected using a sterile knife. Only the meat tissue of the fish and pork was taken. Each meat sample was taken and 25 grams of the meat was mixed with 8 ml of distilled water in a clean blender. The mix was first put into Brain-Heart Infusion broth and kept at 37°C for 24 hours. From the broth, a small number of bacteria was spread on MacConkey's lactose agar and then kept at 37°C for 24 hours. Twelve (12) colonies that were pink or red were taken and spread on Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) Agar. They were again kept at 37°C for 24 hours. Colonies that had a dark center and a flat, green shiny look were believed to be *E. coli*.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test

All the *E. coli* strains that tested positive were then tested to see how well they resisted different antibiotic medicines. This was done using Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) and the disc diffusion method, as advised by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) in 2018.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test

To check for ESBL *E. coli*, the samples that tested positive for *E. coli* were then tested again using the antibiotic susceptibility test with the disk diffusion method. The first step of this process is screening, as identified by the Clinical Laboratory Science Institute (2018). In this process, the samples were tested with antibiotic disks. Afterwards, the zones of inhibition of the bacteria were measured following CLSI (2018) guidelines.

Screening Test for ESBLs

Isolates were tested for antimicrobial sensitivity using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method as per CLSI guidelines. Commercially available discs with cefotaxime (30 µg), ceftriaxone (30 µg), ceftazidime (30 µg), cefpodoxime (10 µg), and aztreonam (30 µg) were used on Mueller Hinton agar plates. Based on CLSI (2018), isolates showing a zone of inhibition of ≤ 27 mm with cefotaxime, ≤ 25 mm with ceftriaxone, ≤ 22 mm with ceftazidime, ≤ 17 mm with cefpodoxime, or ≤ 27 mm with aztreonam were considered possible ESBL producers and were further tested for confirmation.

Double Disk Synergy Test

Double disk synergy test was used as a confirmatory test for ESBL production. A 0.5 McFarland standard isolate was used to inoculate a Mueller-Hinton agar plate. A disk of amoxicillin/clavulanate (20µg/10µg, respectively) and a disc of oxyimino-β-lactam (30µg) were placed 30 mm apart on an inoculated agar plate to detect the synergy between cefotaxime and clavulanate. An increase in the zone of inhibition around oxyimino-β-lactam antibiotics, especially near a clavulanate disk, forming a shape known as “champagne-cork,” “keyhole,” or “phantom image” showed synergy, suggesting the presence of an ESBL. This test can use 30 µg disks of ceftazidime, aztreonam, and ceftriaxone (Paterson & Bonomo, 2005).

Statistical Tool

The statistical method used to compare the significant difference in the number of colony count in meat of fish and pork was T-test. This allowed the researchers to further identify the comparable number of colonies from fish and pork meat sample. This method is also used to find out if there is a significant difference between the averages of two groups that might share their certain features.

Results and Discussion**Table 1.** Bacterial growth detection on MacConkey agar in fish samples (meat tissue)

Public Market	Samples	Fermenter	Growth of Bacteria
Market A	1	LF	Moderate Growth
	2	LF	Heavy Growth
	3	LF, some NLF seen	Light Growth of LF and NLF
Market B	4	LF	Light Growth
	5	NLF	Moderate Growth
	6	LF	Heavy Growth
Market C	7	LF	Light Growth
	8	LF	Light Growth
	9	NLF, some LF seen	Light Growth of LF, Moderate Growth of NLF
Market D	10	LF	Moderate Growth
	11	LF, some NLF seen	Moderate Growth of LF, Light Growth of NLF
	12	LF	Moderate Growth
Market E	13	LF, some NLF seen	Moderate Growth of LF
	14	LF	Heavy Growth
	15	LF, some NLF seen	Heavy Growth of LF, Moderate Growth of NLF

Legend: NLF = Non-lactose fermenter; LF = Lactose-fermenter

Table 1 shows predominance of the growth of lactose-fermenting bacteria in most plates presenting pink colonies on MacConkey agar. Some plates show LF with some NLF seen. Variation of growth pattern of LF can be seen in the samples. Only one sample shows NLF ruling out the presence of *E. coli*.

Table 2. Bacterial growth detection on MacConkey agar in pork samples

Public Market	Samples	Fermenter	Growth of Bacteria
Market A	1	LF	Heavy Growth
	2	NLF	Light Growth
	3	LF	Heavy Growth
Market B	4	LF	Heavy Growth
	5	NLF, some LF seen	Light Growth
	6	LF	Moderate Growth
Market C	7	LF	Heavy Growth
	8	LF	Heavy Growth
	9	NLF, some LF seen	Light Growth
Market D	10	LF	Heavy Growth
	11	LF	Heavy Growth
	12	LF	Moderate Growth
Market E	13	LF	Moderate Growth
	14	LF, some NLF seen	Heavy Growth
	15	LF, some NLF seen	Moderate Growth

Legend: NLF = Non-lactose fermenter; LF = Lactose-fermenter

Table 2 shows predominance of the growth of lactose-fermenting bacteria in most plates presenting pink colonies on MacConkey agar. Moderate to heavy growth pattern of LF is seen in these samples. Some plates show LF with some NLF seen.

Table 3. Bacterial growth detection on EMB agar in fish samples

Public Market	Samples	Color	Growth of Bacteria
Market A	1	Pink, mucoid colonies	Heavy Growth
	2	Green-metallic sheen	Light Growth
	3	Pink colonies	Moderate Growth
Market B	4	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	5	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	6	Green-metallic sheen	Heavy Growth
Market C	7	Pink, mucoid colonies	Heavy Growth
	8	Pink colonies	Moderate Growth
	9	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
Market D	10	Green-metallic sheen	Light Growth
	11	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	12	Green-metallic sheen	Heavy Growth
Market E	13	Green-metallic sheen	Heavy Growth
	14	Blue colonies	Moderate Growth
	15	Pink, mucoid colonies	Moderate Growth

Table 3 shows variations of bacterial growth of colonies in EMB. Five samples show green metallic sheen colonies, presumptive of the presence of *E. coli*. Others show pink and mucoid colonies and colorless colonies, ruling out the presence of *E. coli* in the sample.

Table 4 shows variations of bacterial growth of colonies on EMB. Three samples show presumptive of the presence of *E. coli*, seen as green-metallic sheen colonies. Other samples show pink and mucoid colonies and colorless colonies ruling out the presence of *E. coli* in the sample.

Table 4. Bacterial growth detection on EMB agar in pork samples

Public Market	Samples	Color	Growth of Bacteria
Market A	1	Pink, mucoid colonies	Heavy Growth
	2	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	3	Pink colonies	Moderate Growth
Market B	4	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	5	Pink, mucoid colonies	Heavy Growth
	6	Pink colonies	Moderate Growth
Market C	7	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	8	Green-metallic sheen	Moderate Growth
	9	Green-metallic sheen	Moderate Growth
Market D	10	Colorless colonies	Light Growth
	11	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	12	Blue colonies	Moderate Growth
Market E	13	Green-metallic sheen	Moderate Growth
	14	Colorless colonies	Moderate Growth
	15	Pink, mucoid colonies	Heavy Growth

The green metallic sheen sometimes seen on *E. coli* colonies is not always there and cannot be used alone to confirm that the bacteria is *E. coli*. More biochemical or serological tests should be done on pure culture colonies for proper identification.

Biochemical Test Results

Isolates with a green metallic sheen on EMB agar were tested biochemically to identify *E. coli*. An isolate was considered *E. coli* if it was positive for indole and methyl red tests and negative for Voges-Proskauer and citrate tests (Lupindu, 2017).

Table 5. Biochemical test results: fish samples (meat tissue)

Samples	Sulfide	Indole	Motility	MR	VP	Citrate	TSI	LIA
2	+	-	+	+	+	-	A/A	-/+
6	-	-	+	+	+	-	K/A	-/+
10	+	-	+	+	-	-	A/A	-/+
12	+	-	+	+	+	-	A/A	-/+
13	-	+	+	+	-	-	A/A	-/+

From the results shown in Table 5 for biochemical testing, the fish sample that tested positive for *E. coli* contamination was sample 13 which was obtained from Zapote Market. Sample 13 presented biochemical characteristics with that of *E. coli*, showing respective values (+, +, -, -) on IMViC, negative (-) on sulfide, positive (+) on motility, A/A on TSI and -/+ on LIA and was also a lactose fermenter and has a green-metallic sheen on EMB agar.

Table 6. Biochemical test results: pork samples (meat tissue)

Samples	Sulfide	Indole	Motility	MR	VP	Citrate	TSI	LIA
8	+	-	+	+	+	-	K/A	-/+
9	+	-	+	+	+	-	K/A	-/+
13	-	+	+	+	-	-	A/A	-/+

As for the pork sample in Table 6, sample 13 also showed presence of *E. coli* which was also obtained from Zapote Market. Sample 13 presented biochemical characteristics with that of *E. coli*, showing respective values (+, +, -, -) on IMViC, negative (-) on sulfide, positive (+) on motility, A/A on TSI and -/+ on LIA and was also a lactose fermenter and has a green-metallic sheen on EMB agar.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Test Results

Table 7. ESBL screening test results of confirmed *E. coli* in fish sample

Sample 13	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Ave. Zone of Inhibition	CLSI Criteria	Interpretation
Cefotaxime	34 mm	33 mm	32 mm	33 mm	≤ 27 mm	Susceptible
Ceftazidime	28 mm	29 mm	28 mm	28.33 mm	≤ 22 mm	Susceptible
Aztreonam	32 mm	33 mm	33 mm	32.67 mm	≤ 27 mm	Susceptible
Ceftriaxone	32 mm	29 mm	30 mm	30.33 mm	≤ 25 mm	Susceptible

Based on the measured zone of inhibition shown in table 7, *E. coli* isolate from the fish sample was found not to be ESBL producer as it is susceptible to the four (4) types of antibiotic disks namely, Ceftazidime (CAZ), Aztreonam (ATM), Cefotaxime (CTX), and Ceftriaxone (CRO). The measured zone of inhibition exceeded the criteria recommended by the CLSI. The results were in contrast to a similar study conducted by Iroha et al. (2019) where out of the 21 *E. coli* isolated, at least 7 (33.3%) were ESBL-producers in fish.

Table 8. ESBL screening test results of confirmed *E. coli* in pork sample

Sample 13	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Ave. Zone of Inhibition	CLSI Criteria	Interpretation
Cefotaxime	31 mm	31 mm	33 mm	31.67 mm	≤ 27 mm	Susceptible
Ceftazidime	27 mm	28 mm	30 mm	28.33 mm	≤ 22 mm	Susceptible
Aztreonam	33 mm	32 mm	32 mm	32.33 mm	≤ 27 mm	Susceptible
Ceftriaxone	28 mm	28 mm	28 mm	28 mm	≤ 25 mm	Susceptible

Based on the tabulated results in Table 8, the measured zones of inhibition of the *E. coli* isolate of pork exceeded the criteria recommended by the CLSI and were also found not to be ESBL producers as they are susceptible to the four (4) antibiotics used as opposed to a study conducted by Randall et al. (2017) where out of 397 collected raw meat samples, 2.5% of pork samples were positive for ESBL.

Table 9. Antibiotic Susceptibility Test of *E. coli* in fish and pork to other antibiotics

Product	Sample 13	Zone of Inhibition	CLSI Criteria	Interpretation
Fish	Ampicillin	12 mm	≤ 27 mm	Resistant
	Tetracycline	26 mm	≤ 22 mm	Susceptible
	Imipenem	30 mm	≤ 27 mm	Susceptible
Pork	Ampicillin	15 mm	S = ≥ 17; I = 14-16; R = ≤ 13	Intermediate
	Tetracycline	27 mm	S = ≥ 15; I = 12-14; R = ≤ 11	Susceptible
	Imipenem	30 mm	S = ≥ 23; I = 20-22; R = ≤ 19	Susceptible

The researchers also tested the susceptibility of the positive *E. coli* isolates of fish and pork to antibiotic ampicillin, imipenem, and tetracycline. The results in Table 9 show that the two *E. coli* isolates were sensitive to tetracycline and imipenem antibiotics. The *E. coli* isolate from fish showed resistance to ampicillin with a 12 mm zone of inhibition, while the *E. coli* isolate from pork was intermediate according to CLSI guidelines.

Table 10. Level of ESBL *E. coli* in the various retail fish and pork meat products

Product	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	CFU	Average CFU
Fish	7.4×10^7	7.0×10^7	6.7×10^7	74000000 70000000	70333333.33
Pork	6.6×10^7	6.3×10^7	5.8×10^7	66000000 63000000 58000000	62333333.33

Based on the gathered results in Table 10, the meat from fish has an average of 70333333.33 CFU of *Escherichia coli* while pork has an average of 62333333.33 CFU of *Escherichia coli*. Therefore, the meat in fish shows higher colony count of *Escherichia coli* than pork. It is suggested that contamination of *E. coli* on both samples can be attributed to contaminated water or ice used to store the sample. Handling and transport from the vendor to the consumer can also be a factor of contamination.

Table 11. Independent Samples Test

Variance	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Equal variances assumed	.082	.788	2.588	4	.061	8000000	0.062	Not Significant	Accept
Equal variances not assumed			2.588	3.924	.062	8000000			

Table 11 shows that there is no significant difference between CFUs in meat of the fish and that in the pork; therefore, the null hypothesis has been accepted. This suggests that even though the colony count in fish meat sample is higher than pork meat sample, there is still no significant difference based on the result of the statistical analysis. The colony counts on both meat samples might have exceeded the acceptable limit of CFU count in raw meat; therefore, it is possible that the amount of *Escherichia coli* present in the meat sample may pose a significant health risk to humans, especially those who are at risk factors: young children and young adults, immunocompromised, people who regularly eat meat.

Conclusion

The organisms isolated from fish and pork meat that came from selected public markets in Cavite were identified through biochemical testing. Isolates that presented similar biochemical characteristics with that of *Escherichia coli* were subjected to antimicrobial susceptibility testing for presence of extended spectrum beta-lactamase. Out of 30 samples comprising of 15 fish samples and 15 pork samples, each respective sample obtained from Market E presented similar biochemical characteristics with *Escherichia coli*. Both positive *Escherichia coli* isolates underwent ESBL antimicrobial susceptibility testing and were confirmed non-ESBL producers following CLSI criteria. Based on the data obtained from the experiment, it has been shown through statistical analysis that the fish sample has higher CFU count of *Escherichia coli* than that of the pork sample.

Recommendations

Based on the findings made in the study, the following are the recommendations:

1. It is important to follow proper food handling, storage, and cooking practices to avoid getting foodborne illnesses.
2. Future researchers may conduct similar studies about this topic which cover other Enterobacteriaceae and their strains.
3. Future researchers may conduct studies about this topic using different samples from different locations.
4. Future researchers may use polymerase chain reaction in isolates to detect specific genes.

References

- Allen, M. E. (2005). *MacConkey agar plates protocols*. American Society for Microbiology. <https://asm.org/protocols/macconkey-agar-plates-protocols>
- Aliyu, A. B., Saleha, A. A., Jalila, A., & Zunita, Z. (2016). Risk factors and spatial distribution of extended spectrum β -lactamase-producing-Escherichia coli at retail poultry meat markets in Malaysia: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 16, 699. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3377-2>
- Boss, R., Overesch, G., & Baumgartner, A. (2016). Antimicrobial resistance of Escherichia coli, Enterococci, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, and Staphylococcus aureus from raw fish and seafood imported into Switzerland. *Journal of Food Protection*, 79(7), 1240-1246. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X.JFP-15-463>
- Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. (2018). *CLSI M100: Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing* (28th ed.). Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute.
- Cornista, J. C., Cuña, A. M. D., Sanchez, H. J. A., & Balolong, M. P. (2019). Detection of Extended-spectrum β -Lactamase-producing Klebsiella pneumoniae Isolated from Four Provincial Hospitals in Luzon and Genotyping of β -Lactamase (bla CTX-M, bla TEM, bla SHV, and bla OXA-1) Genes. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 148(2), 277-287. https://philjournalsci.dost.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/detection-of-extended-spectrum-lactamase-producing-K-pneumoniae_.pdf
- Cruz, M. C., Bacani, C. S., Mendoza, A. B., & Hedreyda, C. T. (2014). Evaluation of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase production in Escherichia coli clinical isolates from three hospitals in Luzon, Philippines. *Philippine Science Letters*, 7(2), 438-444. <https://scienggj.org/2014/PSL%202014-vol07-no02-p438-444%20Cruz.pdf>
- Davis, G. S., Waits, K., Nordstrom, L., Grande, H., Weaver, B., Papp, K., Horwinski, J., Koch, B., Hungate, B. A., Liu, C. M., & Price, L. B. (2018). Antibiotic-resistant Escherichia coli from retail poultry meat with different antibiotic use claims. *BMC Microbiology*, 18(1), 174. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-018-1322-5>
- Elena, A., Cejas, D., Magariños, F., Jewtuchowicz, V., Facente, A., Gutkind, G., Di Conza, J., & Radice, M. (2018). Spread of clonally related Escherichia coli strains harboring an IncA/C1 plasmid encoding IMP-8 and its recruitment into an unrelated MCR-1-containing isolate. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 62(6), e02414-17. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.02414-17>
- Elhadi, N. (2016). Prevalence of extended-spectrum- β -lactamase-producing Escherichia coli in imported frozen freshwater fish in Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Journal of Medicine & Medical Sciences*, 4(1), 19-25. https://journals.lww.com/sjmm/Fulltext/2016/04010/Prevalence_of.5.aspx

- Gupta, B., Ghatak, S., & Gill, J. P. S. (2013). Incidence and virulence properties of *E. coli* isolated from fresh fish and ready-to-eat fish products. *Veterinary World*, 6(1), 5-9. <https://www.veterinaryworld.org/Vol.6/January%20-%202013/2.html>
- Harris, P. N., Tambyah, P. A., & Paterson, D. L. (2015). β -lactam and β -lactamase inhibitor combinations in the treatment of extended-spectrum β -lactamase producing Enterobacteriaceae: Time for a reappraisal in the era of few antibiotic options? *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 15(4), 475-485. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(14\)70950-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(14)70950-8)
- Heuer, O. E., Kruse, H., Grave, K., Collignon, P., Karunasagar, I., & Angulo, F. J. (2009). Human health consequences of use of antimicrobial agents in aquaculture. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 49(8), 1248-1253. <https://doi.org/10.1086/605667>
- Iroha, I. R., Okwuchukwu, H. N., Moses, I. B., Nwakaeze, A. E., & Ugbo, E. N. (2019). Isolation of *Pseudomonas* species and extended spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* from retail imported mackerel frozen fishes sold in Abakaliki Metropolis. *Archives of Clinical Microbiology*, 10(3), 93. <https://www.acmicrob.com/abstract/isolation-of-pseudomonas-species-and-extended-spectrum-betalactamase-producing-escherichia-coli-from-retail-imported-mackerel-frozen-fishes-sold-in-abakaliki-metropolis-24526.html>
- James, C. E., Stanley, K. N., Allison, H. E., Flint, H. J., Stewart, C. S., Sharp, R. J., Saunders, J. R., & McCarthy, A. J. (2001). Lytic and lysogenic infection of diverse *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella* strains with a verocytotoxigenic bacteriophage. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 67(9), 4335-4337. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.67.9.4335-4337.2001>
- Kikomeko, H. (2016). Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* found in intestinal tract of *Oreochromis niloticus*. *Uganda Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 17(2), 157-164. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ujas.v17i2.3>
- Lupindu, A. M. (2017). Isolation and characterization of *Escherichia coli* from animals, humans, and environment. In A. Samie (Ed.), *Escherichia coli – Recent advances on physiology, pathogenesis and biotechnological applications* (pp. 187-206). IntechOpen Limited. <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/54411>
- Martínez-Chávez, L., Cabrera-Díaz, E., Pérez-Montaño, J. A., Garay-Martínez, L. E., Varela-Hernández, J. J., Castillo, A., Lucía, L., Ávila-Novoa, M. G., Cardona-López, M. A., Gutiérrez-González, P., & Martínez-González, N. E. (2015). Quantitative distribution of *Salmonella* spp. and *Escherichia coli* on beef carcasses and raw beef at retail establishments. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 210, 149-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2015.06.016>
- Morris, D., Ludden, C., Burke, E., & Cormican, M. (2014). Extended spectrum beta-lactamase producing *E. coli* contamination of chicken meat in the Irish retail market. *Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology and Food Sciences*, 3(5), 419-421. <https://office2.jmbfs.org/index.php/JMBFS/article/view/7008>
- Ojer-Usoz, E., González, D., & Vitas, A. I. (2017). Clonal diversity of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* isolated from environmental, human and food samples. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(7), 676. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14070676>
- Reuland, E. A., Al Naiemi, N., Raadsen, S. A., Savelkoul, P. H. M., Kluytmans, J. A. J. W., & Vandenbroucke-Grauls, C. M. J. E. (2014). Prevalence of ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae in raw vegetables. *European Journal of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases*, 33(10), 1843-1846. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10096-014-2142-7>
- Randall, L. P., Lodge, M. P., Elviss, N. C., Lemma, F. L., Hopkins, K. L., Teale, C. J., & Woodford, N. (2017). Evaluation of meat, fruit and vegetables from retail stores in five United Kingdom regions as sources of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing and carbapenem-resistant *Escherichia coli*. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 241, 283-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2016.10.036>
- Paterson, D. L., & Bonomo, R. A. (2005). Extended-spectrum β -lactamases: A clinical update. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 18(4), 657-686. <https://doi.org/10.1128/cmr.18.4.657-686.2005>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2017). *Consumption of selected agricultural commodities in the Philippines: Volume 2 – By barangay classification*. Philippine Statistics Authority.

- Saad, S. M., Hassanien, F. S., & Mousa, M. (2020). Monitoring of some pathogenic bacteria in Nile fish. *Benha Veterinary Medical Journal*, 38(2), 65-70.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.21608/bvmj.2020.24799.1169>
- Shrestha, A., Bajracharya, A. M., Subedi, H., Turha, R. S., Kafle, S., Sharma, S., Neupane, S., & Chaudhary, D. K. (2017). Multi-drug resistance and extended spectrum beta lactamase producing Gram negative bacteria from chicken meat in Bharatpur Metropolitan, Nepal. *BMC Research Notes*, 10(1), 574. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-017-2917-x>
- Soufi, L., Sáenz, Y., Vinué, L., Abbassi, M. S., Ruiz, E., Zarazaga, M., Hassen, A. B., Hammami, S., & Torres, C. (2011). Escherichia coli of poultry food origin as reservoir of sulphonamide resistance genes and integrons. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 144(3), 497-502.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2010.11.008>
- Tiongco, R. E., Arceo, E., Dizon, D., Navarro, A., Rivera, N., Salita, C., & Singian, E. (2018). Phenotypic evaluation of ESBL-and carbapenemase-producing Escherichia coli and Klebsiella pneumoniae from a teaching hospital in the Philippines. *Tropical Biomedicine*, 35(4), 1064-1074.
<https://msptm.org/files/Vol35No4/1064-1074-Raphael-Enrique-Tiongco.pdf>
- Watts, J. E., Schreier, H. J., Lanska, L., & Hale, M. S. (2017). The rising tide of antimicrobial resistance in aquaculture: Sources, sinks and solutions. *Marine Drugs*, 15(6), 158.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/md15060158>
- World Health Organization. (2014). *Antimicrobial resistance: Global report on surveillance*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241564748>